

Incidence of Food Sourcing in the Niger Delta, AD 1000-2010: AN Exhibition Report and Analysis

Stanley I. Okoroafor
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt-Nigeria

Abstract

The Niger Delta is a region of latest human settlement and adaptation in Nigeria. This stems from the young age of the emergence of habitable land which was later occupied by some 'primitive' Nigerians following the 'Recent' regression of the Atlantic. Since about the last three millennia, humans in this area have struggled to situate themselves in the most appropriate manners. One of such means of adaptation is the incidence of food sourcing in the Delta. Food being a basic need of man, has always taken primary place in his concerns. The 'water life' of the people in the region tilts most of the people's actions in that direction yet there have been other terrestrial activities including those of food sourcing in which they have shown good knowledge of. In the University of Port Harcourt Museum, effort has been made to specially collect, preserve and exhibit the elements and objects of such adaptation, in order to properly evaluate the typology, form and development of these in a segregated chronological order. The peoples and governments of the Niger Delta area are by the result of this research, being nudged to look inwards, and be environmentally conscious so as to have a more sustainable and effective development, for a happier living of all in the Delta.

Key words: Food Sourcing, Niger Delta, Artifacts, Exhibition, Sustainable Development.

Résumé

Le Niger Delta est une région de la dernière habitation humaine et adaptation au Nigéria. Cela vient du jeune âge de l'émergence de ces terres habitables qui ont ensuite été occupées par des Nigériens «primitifs» suite à la régression «récente» de l'Atlantique. Depuis environ trois millénaires, les humains de cette région se sont efforcés de se situer de la manière la plus appropriée. Un de ces moyens d'adaptation est l'incidence de l'approvisionnement alimentaire dans le delta. La nourriture étant un besoin fondamental de l'homme, a toujours pris une place primordiale dans ses préoccupations. La «vie aquatique» des populations de la région oriente la plupart des actions des populations vers cette direction, mais il y a eu d'autres activités terrestres dont celles de l'approvisionnement alimentaire pour lesquelles elles ont montré une bonne connaissance. Au Musée de l'Université de Port Harcourt, des efforts ont été faits pour collecter, préserver et exposer spécialement les éléments et les objets d'une telle adaptation, afin d'en évaluer correctement la typologie, la forme et le développement dans un ordre chronologique séparé. Les peuples et les gouvernements de la région du Niger Delta sont, à la suite de cette recherche, priés de regarder vers l'intérieur et d'être soucieux de l'environnement afin d'avoir un développement plus durable et efficace, pour une vie plus heureuse dans le Niger Delta.

Mots-clés: Approvisionnement alimentaire, Niger Delta, Artefacts, Exposition, Survivance

Introduction

The various efforts of pioneer scholars, administrators, adventurers, traders and the clergy in

the Niger Delta exposed widely, some of the region's objects and elements of adaptation especially the ones that are used in sourcing for food. The region has experienced vibrant internal and external trade activities within about the last five hundred years. First, was at the initial entrance of some Europeans at the coast and the introduction of the first line of Article Trade. This was followed by the Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade and the subsequent Produce Trade (especially on palm oil and kernel). These contacts were occasioned by exchange of not just the trade items (through barter) or through some other medium of exchange but with associated ideas and many other aspects of interaction together with their material representations (Margery 1960; Alagoa, 2005; Okorobia, 1999).

These notwithstanding, the early prehistoric researches including those on excavations by F.N. Anozie, N.C. Nzewunwa, R.K. Williamson, M.A. Sowunmi, A.A. Derefaka and lately S.I. Okoroafor all in consonance with E.J. Alagoa, revealed the various aspects of the socio-economic life of the people of the area. It was through such researches that much of the uniqueness of the people's manners of coping with the situation of the Delta was brought to the limelight. This was such that numerous artifacts of such life-ways of the people recovered were sorted into about fifty classifications (Derefaka 1997, 2003). Some of these within reach were selected and were supported with the ethnographic associates and organized into an exhibition at the University of Port Harcourt Museum with a view to properly evaluate the typology and form within the matrix of the Delta's development.

The Exhibition Plan

The gallery of the University of Port Harcourt Museum has a small space of 10m width and 18m length. The main house door opens into it from where one can access the other sections of the building through a smaller door to the opposite side of the main entrance door. The two horizontal sides of the gallery have windows all through which are only separated by the small walls in between. The gallery therefore, is airy and fairly illuminated. The roof is high and the lighting points adequate. A small section of the gallery has been cordoned off has strict usage to the serve as a workshop and handling room. The props are not adequate but some improvisations have been made to the effect that the place is carefully and methodically managed. Some of the fitted blinds in the gallery depict the cultural background on which the exhibition is being put-up. With sharp paint fixed on the walls, and the radiant rug carpet on the floor of the gallery, the place wore a beautiful warm ambience. The props were then arranged in manners that visitors to the exhibition would go into it through the main door (a double door, wide enough to freely pass at least two persons moving abreast into the gallery), turn left to the general information section. This has two tables: a big one with two platforms in the middle, a small 'Table of Welcome' as we call it to its left and a large portrait to the right, at the front of which there is a burst. The exhibition then takes a southward turn with four showcases properly aligned and separated. At the end of these stretch of showcases, the exhibition takes a right (westward) turn with a table covered with both satin cloth and George wrappers with exotic rims used in decorating the first set of tables standing opposite this at the entrance. The direction of the exhibition then turns northwards towards the entrance. On this, can be found, three decorated tables gracefully aligned along and across that establishes a degree of harmony. This stops short

around the door so as to allow the visitors turn without stumbling on the structures, to the reverse side of the stretch of tables. On this side, brilliantly coloured screens are also mounted to kind of viel the first section of the exhibition and to provide the platform on which the next is to be presented. There were three of these screens behind the tables earlier mentioned. At the end these channels, one turns right again to a highly raised platform that has been decorated in Nigeria's national colour of 'green white green' facing the main entrance.

The exhibition moves on westward by the right to the final stretch of equally decorated tables and variously coloured screens (shielding off the workshop room), in between which there are some significant objects of interest. This leads one back to the entrance and the end of the exhibition. One can then move back into the other areas of the museum through the smaller door down south, where a small table decorated in a special manner has a visitors' notebook on commendation/remark or as he or she exits the place. The window panes and door panels were thoroughly cleaned and polished. The small corners of the gallery have flower vases hanging or standing to further embellish the place.

The Constituents of the Exhibition

The items put up in this exhibition were particularly chosen to express the history and cultural development of food sourcing among the Niger Delta people in the most vivid manner to educate, inform and entertain the audience. They fall into the antiques and replicas of the objects and elements of the adaptation. As earlier noted however, there were other related museum items placed around these to enhance the exhibition in one way or another. For instance, being in the University museum, there were a few other materials (of images, art works, sculptures etc.) carefully placed at different areas of the gallery adding to the embellishment All these were informed by the historical knowledge of the incidence of food production in the region. As a result of this, a quick review of such would suffix to flash back into this history so to understand the rationale behind the exhibition process.

The Niger Delta (the area to the southernmost part of Nigeria and some other areas of the south east and south west, covering nine states of Nigeria, namely: Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Rivers, Abia, Imo and Ondo States) has been occupied in parts and at different times in accordance with the evolution of the land. In the upland areas, the incidence of food sourcing began with the occupation of this place by man. It therefore, began with the hunting and gathering and some incipient agriculture. As the land emerged from the northern going to the southern parts of the Delta, more and more people entered the region adapting unto it accordingly (in fishing, hunting and some level of cropping) Sowunmi (1987), Alagoa (2005), Nzewunwa (1988 & 1983). There were however, some other Nigerians (the Ijo, Itshekiri, Oru, Andoni, Kalabari, Nembe and Efik-Ibibio groups) who had earlier been around the Delta with less land availability, adapting into it in special 'water-life' (peculiar behaviour associated to water bodies dealings and mannerisms. Some of these ethnic groups, until today, have not bothered much about other means of food production but specializing in different aquatic resources derivations. These take much of the attention in the Niger Delta affairs including the food sourcing overtime. It is for this reason that some persons would not have other people outside considered as the true or core Niger Delta area/people. Even as they take the front line discussion pertaining to the region, the

others not dwelling so deep into the Delta also bring about their experience of the Delta which make for a more complete accounting for the historical and cultural knowledge of the land and people.

The Exhibition

The items of exhibition collated therefore, consisted of some lithic, wooden and metal wares, to some textile and synthetic stuffs involved in sourcing for food in the region. These were placed in a chronological order, in accordance to the history and cultural acquisition. The mainstream Delta area does not hold much stone of tools compared to those to the upland, but it experienced use of stone in either acquiring or processing food. The stone tools were show-cased as the first line of evidence of food sourcing by the Niger Delta people. There were though some general items of information on the theme of the exhibition on the first channel.

These stone tools included those obtained from the Ugwu-Ele Uturu excavation in today's Abia State Nigeria's excavation. These were hand axes, cores, scrappers and discs on one hand, grinding stones and the 'pestle', some grains and dried leaves such as tobacco, pepper, melon, tomatoes and dried yam flakes on the other .

These were followed in the next showcase by the wooden materials for food sourcing, processing and dishing such as the carved wooden double portion plates, calabash/gourd plates and cups and metal plates. Next to this is another showcase in which were some clay wares such as bowls, caps, plates and small pots. These represented an advancement in the food processing and dishing. The items represented the utensils of the period from between the dusk of the Late Stone Age and the Neolithic which marks the beginning of food production. The objects on clay were arranged sequentially depicting the history of their working and usage. Below standing on the floor were two big clay vessels: for immersing of food and big hemispherical pot for storage of water, alcohol, drug etc. The last showcase on this role has in it, an artistic (craft) working of a special fence trap for fishing found in the Niger Delta called *ifaa* by the Oru people of the region, three small fishing basket-like traps woven in the particular manners found in the area.

The table standing directly opposite the first one at the beginning of the exhibition, has on it, information on fishing in the forms of fishing gears made using cane (woven baskets traps such as *snkwu*). On it are displayed, nets, beginning with the vegetable type referred to by some as *akpuruka*, to the nylon types fixed on a round frame on the handle/head, with dropping net of different shapes and mesh sizes. There were also, variously shaped and sized fishing baskets. For example *akpara* and *mgbaya* and food processing (winnowing trays) called *utita*, fish storing and carriage type called *dukpa* or *abo* and *ekete*, and two big calabash containers (for preserving certain life fish). The exhibition takes a turn towards the exit along which there are the three decorated tables for holding some materials of it. The first one has on it, full caste nylon net known as *ochokoro*, the trap net, which is usually fixed vertically across a given water body to trap fish when they try to swim through it, nylon thread (including the tiny 'magic rope') and variously sized hooks for fishing, the wooden holders called *ogugu-nchu* and *igbo*, and the *marimarimass* hook type. Others are iron traps for mainly rodents called *onya-igwe*, metal cage trap made with Wire Goss of small mesh sizes, different kinds of spear such as *okayi*, *oyoo*, *okponi* and

mkpara-egbe, metal arrow point, bow and arrow, cutlasses and knives (of different shapes and sizes). On the next table, were more items of the regions' food processing and dishing.

The table standing directly opposite the first one at the beginning of the exhibition, has on it, information on fishing in the forms of fishing gears made of cane (woven baskets traps like *nkwu*), featuring particularly, nets beginning with the vegetable type (*akpuruka*) to the nylon types fixed on road frame on the handle/head, with dropping net of different shapes and mesh sizes. There were also, fishing baskets of various shapes and sizes for fishing. Some of such are *akpara* and *mgbaya*, and food processing wares such as winnowing trays known as *utita*, fish storing and carriage devices such as *asukpa* or *abo* and *ekete*, and two big calabash containers (for preserving life fish) called *itinkoro*. The exhibition then takes a turn towards the exit along which there are the three decorated tables that some more objects of food processing and associated elements. The first one has on it, full-cast nylon net called *ochokoro*, the trap net called *eriri* which is usually fixed vertically across a given water body to trap fish when they try to swim through it, nylon thread (including the thirty magic cape) and variously sized hooks for fishing, the wooden holder (*ogugu*, *ndu* and *igbo*), the *mariari* mess hook type, iron traps for mainly rodents, metal cage trap made with wire gross of mesh sizes, spear *okai*, *oyoo*, *okponi* and *mkpara egbe*, metal arrow point, bow and arrow, cutlasses and knives (of different shapes sizes) on the next table were further items of the rejoins food processing.

These included, grinding stone, big and small wooden mortars and the pestles, earthen ware bowls, plates, small table pots (for seasonings) *angala* (*mgbara*), *abara*, *ngiga*, *mkpodu*, *kasa* (for drying fish and meat), *utita* (for separation/filtration, sunning and exposing food items such as yam, cassava, plantain, banana and potato flakes for making of the floor (*ariba/alibo*), crayfish, *agbono* and *egusi* (melon). Below the table are some more jars for storing/preserving, fermenting and similar processing of food. This is the final stage of further processing/cooking of the food and serving them. The items were numbered and the labeling made on the panel/screen above on the objects on the table of exhibition. The next is a table that is used in concluding the story of the incidence of food in the Delta. On this channel called "Eat and Relax", are a decorated table, the aligned panel with the identification and description of the items on display. The items included differently sized and coloured Marrakesh, traditional wooden and metal gongs and their handles. Others are flutes, local hand guitar, clappers, interesting musical drums, wooden and metal rattles, and beads for dancing such as *jigida*, empty beer bottle and a table spoon (this complements the bottle as a musical set of the people). There were also two small masks for feminine masquerade display, raffia cloth with Ekpo and Ibom symbols on them, few special clothes of the Niger Delta such as *ikakibite*, *akuruaku/akwaete*, *omu-aru*, *akwa-ocha* and *egenebita* used in ceremonies and entertainment, and a set of *okwe/njorokoto* game on a specially designed carved wood casing.

It is on this happy note that the exhibition draws to an end and one has the option of exiting from the main door or going backwards out through the back door down the hall way. The person may wish to attend to the 'Note-Book' of remark placed on a small but exotically decorated table at the beginning of the hall way towards the exit door to put down in writing, his feeling concerning the exhibition before he leaves. On this table, is the FESTAC FACE MASK (the famous ancient Benin carved face of Queen Idia used as the

mascot or symbol of the Festival of African Cultures {FESTAC} celebrated by most African nations in Lagos, Nigeria in 1977), a very small finely woven basket containing different kinds of candies and chewing gum. The FESTAC FACE symbolizes the strength, civility, beauty and excellence of the Niger Delta in West Africa.

Discussion

The exhibition provided a decent display of how the manners of adaptation of the people of the Niger Delta to the region's unique environment have evolved through the years to become what is obtained therein till date. The preferences of the people rather than just compulsion are observed in the incidence of food production of the various areas of it (the mangrove forest; the swampy rainforest, and the main land Delta to the north, within the palm forest belt of southern Nigeria but with the characteristic wetness and ever-green vegetation of the region). From the first channel, one observes that the people of the Delta merely followed the mainstream technological acquisition for appropriation of especially the food resources. The earliest forms of devices applied unto the food production industry being those of wood, bone and stone. The core areas of the region would not provide much of the latter but the importance of it as the industry developed, further justified its acquisition from the nearby place of Ugwuele in Uturu near Okigwe in Abia State. The stone tools served as evidence of direct linkage between the coastal dwellers and other peoples of the Delta to the hinterland of south-central Nigeria.

Stones were preferred in cracking some nuts, getting bone marrow, hunting some animals and functioning in similar areas of the industry. The stones took over as the technological base of the areas as it did in other places. The folks used them together with the wooden/vegetable devices and the bone implements so that none was finally eliminated as they continued to complement each other till now. Moving further to the other channels and evaluating their forms and contents, one simply comes to the realization of the ingenious measures adopted by the people of the region to master the environment and successfully operate in it. The intersecting of the techniques in the various aspects of the industry within the Delta, from for example the vegetable net such as *akpuruka* to the nylon cast net; the harnessing of bone harpoons to long wooden spears and the advancement from using just the conical cane trap such as *nkwu* to the metal cage equivalent in both fishing and hunting of mainly rodents are all indicative of the process of change in the Delta sometimes stimulated by the changes noticed in the wider area of the sub-Saharan Africa. In some cases, the new level of technology has not been adopted above the old. Some of the older practices are observed to be preferred to the new ones. For instance, the lithic wares but especially the wooden plates are judged more functional than the metal or plastic ones not just in keeping with the tradition, preparing and serving such meals as *owo* (among the Urhobo) or *banga* (among the Efik-Ibibio) or *ofe-akwu* (among the Igboid group), *ishi-ewu* and *nkwobi*. Nigerians around the Delta would prefer the use of wooden or lithic utensils as *mgbekere* and *okwa-oji* to those of metals and plastics.

In similar vein, folks here would prefer the use of vegetable cups such as *mbele* in drinking their palm oil tree (*nkwu*) or raffia palm tree (*ngwo*) wine sometimes served to savour meals or processed horn-cup, to glass, metal and plastic cups.

Among some Oru, Ogbaru, Ukwuani, Ika and Enuani people of south-central Nigeria to the

northern fringes of the Niger Delta, families often would gladly serve and eat the yam foofoo and *nsara* soup called *mbaze* in the very mortar the foofoo was pounded. Sometimes a special delicacy of the dried fish or meat soup to go with the yam foofoo which is not cooked called *oseani* is prepared and eaten right from the mortar. Such define the dietary pattern of the people and are cherished by everybody among them.

Conclusion

There has been, as, it is observable in the channels of the exhibition, good degree of association among the people of the Delta so that there are many common features of the food processing activities in the area. These occur in appropriating aquatic resources such as bailing of ponds, use of cast and drag nets and many other kinds of trap in the waters which are commonly shared among the people. Their interactions lead to dissemination ideas, services and products. In this way, they ensure maximal benefit of especially the food resources so that salt water fish and such 'sea food' can be enjoyed in the fresh water areas and vice versa and people can follow the trend of seasonal harvesting of fish and related aquatic resources for instance. Some of these are smoked and preserved and taken to distant markets of the area and even beyond. The aspect of relaxation with some entertainment and games after eating food as depicted in the exhibition which is like icing of the cake, provides one with further information on how the people of the Delta treasure and celebrate themselves within and outside the family. Working (producing food) and playing in the region often feature in associative manners. The common manner of dance of the Delta region for instance, in which the dancer bends forward and rocks his or her butt, is said to be a re-enactment of fish movement in the water. Again many of the masquerades are fashioned after some of such Delta's aquatic life. The by-products of the food industry have been most beneficial in the textile industry (Cyril-Egware, 2014), architecture (Connah, 1975), entertainment (Krama, 2013), the people's body, pot (Umor, 2014), wall and similar surface decorations and even the Spirituality of the people. The exhibition can be further appreciated in these dimensions and more but most importantly, it has illuminated the special ways of adaptation of the people in their preferred land of adaptation.

References

- Alagoa, E.J. (1972). "Stereotypes in Oral Tradition" *Ikenga*. Nsukka. (1), 1992.
- Alagoa, E.J. (2005). *A History of the Niger Delta: An Historical Interpretation of Ijo Oral Tradition*. Ibadan: IUP.
- Cyril-Egware, P.I. (2015). "Abadi-a-ingo: A Design Alternative for Nembe Se Identity in Textile and Fashion". Unpublished PhD Thesis Submitted to the Department of Fine Arts and Design, University of Port Harcourt.
- Derefaka, A.A.(2003). *Archaeology and Cultural History of Central Niger Delta*. Port Harcourt: Onyeoma.
- Margery, P. (1960). *Luggard: The Years of Authority, 1898-1945*. London.
- Marion J. (1970). "The Cowries Currencies of West Africa". Parts 1&2 *Journal of African History*, xi, (1), p. 33, and xi, (3), p. 331.
- Nzewunwa, N.C. (1983) *A Source Book for Nigerian Archaeology*. Lagos: NCMM, Owerri.

- Nzewunwa, N.C. (1979) "The Niger Delta: Aspects of its Pre-history Economy and Culture". (Ph.D Thesis. St. John College. Cambridge)
- Okoroafor, S. I. (2017), *Niger Delta Prehistory: Oguta (AD 1290-1891)*. Port Harcourt: Onyeoma.
- Okorobia, A. M (1999). "A History of the Underdevelopment of the Eastern Niger Delta AD 1500-1993" (Doctoral Dissertation University of Port Harcourt. Port Harcourt).
- Sowunmi A. A. (1987). "Environment: Past, Present, and Future" in *Foundations of West Africa's Past. WAJA Special Book Issue*. Vol. 17
- Umor, J.J. (2014). "Ibibio Pottery, 1000AD – 2000AD: A Historical Perspective". Unpublished PhD Thesis Submitted to the Department of History and Diplomatic Studies, University of Port Harcourt.
- Williamson, R.K. (1988). "The Linguistic Pre-History of the Niger Delta" in E.J., Alagoa., F.N. Anozie & Nzewunwa, N.C. (eds). *The Early History of the Niger Delta*. Hamburg: Helmut Buske-verlag.
- Williamson, R.K. (1988). "The Pre-degree of Nations: Historical Linguistics in Nigeria". Inaugural Lectures, No. 5, University of Port Harcourt Press.